

A reproducibility study on: "Random Sampling Plus Fake Data: Multidimensional Frequency Estimates With Local Differential Privacy" by H. Arcolezi, J. Couchot, B. Al Bouna and X. Xiao

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Abstract

Local differential privacy (LDP) enables users to protect their data before sending it to the server. Frequently, the server wants to estimate the number of users for each value in multiple attributes ($d \geq 2$). To do this, the privacy budget must be managed carefully due to the composition theorem. Two known solutions are splitting the privacy budget for each attribute (Spl) and random sampling one attribute with all the privacy budget (Smp). Smp has proven to have higher data utility than Spl, but the sampled attribute is visible to the server. The paper[1] we chose proposes a new solution, Random Sampling plus Fake Data (RS+FD), which generates fake data to protect the sampled attribute and uses amplification by sampling. RS+FD is said to achieve the same or better utility than Smp and this claim was supposedly validated using synthetic and real-world data sets. The goal of this paper is to try to reproduce already existing solution, which is previously described, as well as do the significance testing in order to confirm these results.

1 CONTEXT OF THE PROBLEM

Differential privacy (DP), the current standard for data privacy, has gained popularity in recent years. A dependable (usually trusted) aggregator can do calculations on all of the users' raw data in the centralized model of DP (e.g., the Census Bureau). By trusted, we mean that aggregators don't abuse or disclose peoples' private information. In reality, this presumption is not always true. With the local model of DP (LDP), non-trusted services are addressed by having each user apply a DP mechanism to their own data before sending it to a non-trusted aggregator. The LDP paradigm enables data collection in never-before-seen ways, which has encouraged industry to adopt it in a number of ways.

When conducting data collection, multidimensional data can be encountered regularly nowadays. For example, in cloud services, gathering demographic information such as age and gender, as well as user habits, can help to provide a deeper understanding of specific groups and lead to the development of more targeted solutions. Similarly, in digital patient records, users may be associated with both demographic and clinical data. In the paper we are examining, the authors look into the problem of estimating frequency (or histogram) of multiple attributes under LDP. This is a primary goal of the data collector which decodes all of the users' privatized data and estimates the number of users for each possible value, which should remain similarly distributed to the original data.

In recent studies, collecting multidimensional data with LDP has generally focused on numerical data, while this paper tackles the problem of categorical data. To ensure LDP, two solutions have been suggested: splitting the privacy budget for each attribute and sending all randomized values (Spl) or randomly sampling a single attribute and spending the entire privacy budget to send it (Smp). For both methods, one of two state-of-the-art

mechanisms for LDP is used. These are Generalized randomized response (GRR) and Optimized unary encoding (OUE, which has two different possibilities for encoding: OUE-z and OUE-r), which could be also combined in a single Adaptive mechanism (Adp). Spl has been proven to provide lower data utility while Smp adds sampling error, yet it has been shown to provide higher utility. However, regarding Smp, users who sample some kind of sensitive attribute might not be as willing to share their data as users that sampled for example a demographic attribute. This raises the question: Is there a solution for multidimensional frequency estimates that provides better data utility than Spl and more protection than Smp?

1.1 Paper solution

Figure 1 depicts an overview of Random Sampling plus Fake Data (RS+FD), method which is proposed by authors, in comparison to the previously mentioned solutions, Spl and Smp. RS+FD has two client-side steps: local randomization of sampled attribute using LDP mechanism and fake data generation for the rest of the attributes. As a result of the privatized data being "hidden" among fake data, the sampling result is not disclosed along with the users' report (and statistics).

Fig. 1. Overview of our random sampling plus fake data (RS+FD) solution in comparison with two known solutions, namely, Spl and Smp

2 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The first set of experiments we describe are the ones which are used in the paper. Those experiments were mostly based on using diverse data sets (synthetic and real-world) in order to examine how the proposed solution performs in different settings, as opposed to the current state-of-the-art solutions. Our own experiments consisted of running the provided code in order to check whether the given results were reproducible, as well as performing significance testing which was not done in the original paper. The goal is to evaluate their statement that their solution is at least as good as the state-of-the-art solution, if not even better. All experiments were done in Jupyter Notebook with Python 3.8.8, Numpy 1.19.5, Pandas 1.2.4 and Numba 0.53.1.

2.1 Data Sets

The experiments were conducted on two different types of data sets. The main difference between data sets used for experiments are:

- number of features,
- number of samples,
- domain size of feature (range).

The paper's first set of experiments are conducted on six *Synthetic data sets*. The distribution of values in each attribute follows a uniform distribution, for all synthetic data sets.

When it comes to *Real-world data sets*, experiments were done on the following data sets:

- Nursery. [2] A data set from the UCI machine learning repository with $d = 9$ categorical attributes and $n = 12960$ samples.
- Adult. [3] A data set from the UCI machine learning repository with $d = 9$ categorical attributes and $n = 45222$ samples after cleaning the data.
- MS-FIMU.[4] An open dataset from with $d = 6$ categorical attributes and $n = 88935$ samples.
- Census-Income. [5] A data set from the UCI machine learning repository with $n = 33$ categorical attributes and $n = 299285$ samples.

2.2 Evaluation and metrics

The used evaluation metric for results is Mean-Squared-Error (MSE) between the frequency of the hidden data and the frequency of the original data before any of the privacy preserving methods were done. It is averaged per the number of attributes d , and following solutions were considered for evaluation and comparison: Smp[Adp], Spl[Adp], RS+FD[Adp], RS+FD[GRR], RS+FD[OUE-r] and RS+FD[OUE-z].

3 REPRODUCING WORKFLOW

The source code was provided on GitHub [6] for MS-FIMU data set and one of the synthetic data sets. The references to all real world data sets were stated, as well as the needed parameters to generate the rest of the synthetic data sets. However, there were few things that we needed to adapt.

For synthetic data sets, we created 5 more files, by copying the whole notebook and then changing the part related to creation of data set, where we put different parameters. For real-world data sets, we had more work done regarding the preprocessing step. Namely, original data sets contained categorical and other types of data which are not considered in this paper work. This type of data had to be removed. However, after removing all the explicit non categorical data, we would still be left with more attributes than it was stated in the paper. It was not clear which attributes should be removed next.

All other parts of provided code were left the same, and after we run the notebooks we got nearly the same results as in the paper. On the figures below, we compare the results for the MS-FIMU data set. The given figures are mean values of MSE calculated with 100 different seeds, for 6 different values for privacy budget. On Figure 4 our results can be seen, while on Figure 5 results of the original paper can be seen.

Fig. 2. Our results

Fig. 3. Paper results

3.1 Difficulties with data sets and execution

As was previously mentioned we had some difficulties with having to guess how the preprocessing was done, as not everything was stated by the authors clearly. Furthermore, for example in the case of Adult and Census-income data sets, train and test set were divided, so we needed to merge it. For adult data set, they just stated how many rows the final set should have, without mentioning which ones we should remove, so we concluded that those should be the rows with missing values. Also, the problem with income attribute value was that it is an attribute with two possible values " $\leq 50K$ " and " $\geq 50K$ ", while some rows had values " $\leq 50K.$ " and " $\geq 50K.$ ", so we needed to correct this.

The results for Adult data set were not completely the same as in the paper, which might be due to the fact that the preprocessing wasn't clearly stated. On the Figure 4 and 5 we can see results that are not completely the same.

Fig. 4. Our results

Fig. 5. Paper results

Also for Census-Income data set they only gave information about the number of used attributes. They didn't give the exact number of unique values for all of the used attributes, resulting in it being even more challenging to guess which attributes should be kept.

For some synthetic data sets (those that had 500k instances) we didn't manage to run the whole code as it was too much time consuming. We decided to run only the cells which computed the results for Smp[Adp] and RS+FD[Adp] as they seemed to perform the best overall among all the data sets. Even this proved to be taking too much time, as RS+FD[Adp] would run for more than six hours. Additionally, two of the synthetic data sets (data set with $d = 10$, uniform domain size $k = [10, 10, \dots, 10]$, and $n = 500000$, and data set with $n = 500000$, $d = 10$ and domain size $k = [10, 20, \dots, 90, 100]$) were proving to have too long of a runtime so we decided not to finish them because of the limited resources.

3.2 Significance testing

We are using significance testing to determine whether the observed difference between two samples is likely due to the chance or if due to the fact that one method has better performance than the other one. In our case, we set a threshold for significance level to be equal to 0.05.

Since the methods are performed on the same data, the samples of MSE are dependent samples. Therefore, we decided to use the paired t-test. The paired t-test can be used in the case of normally distributed samples, with the same variance. However, in practice, it could be used even if one of the requirements is not full-filled because this test is very robust. In our case, for each data set we used the Levene’s test to check if the variances are significantly different. Sometimes we even got the results that say that they are significantly different, but anyways, we still proceeded with the paired t-test. For checking the distribution, we computed the histograms, and all the samples turned to be normally distributed, which could be seen on the Figure 6 below.

Fig. 6. Histograms of MSE values from 100 different seeds obtained with two different methods for Census-Income data set for privacy budget value of 0.6931.

Significance testing was separately done for small, medium and large privacy budget possibilities. The paired t-test was done with `ttest_rel` function from `scipy.stats` library. For this test we had the following hypothesis: Null hypothesis (H_0)- There is no difference in the mean MSE of method 1 and method 2 (mean MSE for method 1 = mean MSE for method 2), Alternative hypothesis (H_a): There is a difference in the mean MSE of method 1 and method 2 (mean MSE for method 1 \neq mean MSE for method 2), where the method 1 is RD+FD[Adp] and method 2 is Smp[Adp]. If null hypothesis is rejected, to determine which method has better performance, we compared the means of the two methods to check which one is lower (the one with lower value is better).

The results were as follows: for the low values of privacy budget, we always got the results that the mean values of MSE were significantly different (with the p-value being even of the order of magnitude about 10^{-40}). Moreover, when comparing the exact values of MSE for both methods, we got the results that the RS+FD[Adp] had the lower value. For the high values of privacy budget it was the opposite, meaning that the mean values were also significantly different, but this time the mean value of MSE was lower for Smp[Adp]. In the middle values of privacy budget, it was often the case that we couldn’t reject the null-hypothesis (particularly for the synthetic data sets), which means that we cannot say that the mean values are significantly different, but sometimes Smp[Adp] was better (particularly for the real world data sets).

Table 1 represents the p-values for all the combinations of data sets and the privacy budget values that we used for performing paired t-test. The corresponding values of privacy were stated in the code.

Data set	low privacy budget	medium privacy budget	high privacy budget
synthetic1	2.88×10^{-35}	0.93	7.03×10^{-10}
synthetic2	2.35×10^{-37}	0.0015	1.82×10^{-9}
synthetic3	5.13×10^{-45}	0.65	6.52×10^{-20}
synthetic6	1.09×10^{-59}	2.95×10^{-103}	1.01×10^{-102}
Adult	3.74×10^{-22}	0.4	4.25×10^{-8}
Census-Income	7.96×10^{-43}	0.37×10^{-3}	5.17×10^{-24}
Nursery	0.15×10^{-2}	9.88×10^{-19}	2.12×10^{-21}
MS-FIMU	5.93×10^{-26}	0.27	4.40×10^{-7}

Table 1. p-values for corresponding paired t-test.

synthetic1 is data set with $d = 5$, uniform domain size $k = [10, 10, \dots, 10]$, and $n = 50000$, synthetic2 is data set with $d = 5$, uniform domain size $k = [10, 10, \dots, 10]$, and $n = 500000$, synthetic3 is data set with $d = 10$, uniform domain size $k = [10, 10, \dots, 10]$, and $n = 50000$, synthetic6 is data set with $d = 20$, domain size $k = [10, 10, 20, \dots, 100, 100]$ and $n = 500000$.

4 FINDINGS AND CONCLUSIONS

The authors of the paper argued that their method achieves nearly the same, or even better performance than Smp, in addition to overcoming the Smp's shortcoming of it not being fair to some users due to the random sampling of attributes. We could see that that was often the case for the lower privacy budget, but for high values of privacy budget, Smp had smaller MSE. Furthermore, we also confirmed their conclusion that the runtime for their solution was much greater than the one for Smp. Regarding the reproducibility of the paper, most of the crucial information was given, but there is still some room for improvement. For example, while the code for the methodology of the experiment was completely transparent, the details of preprocessing were not always available. The experiment was done for 100 different seeds, on the other hand there was no significant testing done.

REFERENCES

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- [4] MS-FIMU dataset: <https://paperswithcode.com/dataset/ms-fimu>
- [5] Census-Income dataset: <https://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml/datasets/census+income>
- [6] Code: <https://github.com/hharcolezi/ldp-protocols-mobility-cdrs>